

16S haplotypes of “*Candidatus Liberibacter europaeus*” revisited

Warrick R. Nelson

The New Zealand Institute for Plant and Food Research Limited, Private Bag 4704, Christchurch, New Zealand

Plain Language Summary

Haplotypes are an indication of genetic variation within a species and can assist to determine changes in geographic spread, changes in population composition, and potentially the growth characteristics of the organism. An earlier analysis of the 16S rRNA gene, a highly conserved gene in bacteria, suggested the presence of two haplotypes in “*Candidatus Liberibacter europaeus*” that also coincide with variation in plant/psyllid hosts and geographic range. Further, one appears to cause no symptoms in its plant host, while the other produces symptoms. This analysis uses more recently available sequences to confirm the haplotypes.

Abstract

The two tentatively identified 16S haplotypes of “*Candidatus Liberibacter europaeus*” are confirmed in this analysis from more recently available sequences, and a possible third haplotype is suggested. These three haplotypes also confirm the presence of geographic ranges and host-species compositions. Thus we have the first haplotype, LeuA, primarily associated asymptotically with the pear psyllid and its plant hosts around the Mediterranean region, LeuB primarily associated symptomatically with a broom psyllid and its host plants in the United Kingdom and adventive in New Zealand, and LeuC, tentatively, from Japan from the mulberry psyllid.

Phylogenetic placement, originally signalled as being closest to “*Candidatus Liberibacter americanus*” is also confirmed, based on the currently available full length 16S gene sequences.

Introduction

Liberibacter species are α -proteobacteria (Pseudomonadota) (Jagoueix et al. 1994), phloem-limited in their plant host, where they are introduced via the phloem-feeding behaviour of their psyllid (Sternorrhyncha) alternate hosts (Munyanza 2010, Haapalainen 2014, Bové 2019).

Only one *Liberibacter*, *L. crescens* (Fagen et al. 2014), is recognised as a non-*Candidatus* species and is considered remote from the other species (Nelson et al. 2013). In almost all cases, species have been discovered because of the presence of plant symptoms, particularly in economically important plants (Bové 2014, Haapalainen 2014). *Liberibacter* spp. have a circular genome of ~1.4M bp and GC% in the range 31-37% (Chambers et al. 2020).

The bacterial 16S rRNA gene has long been recognised as a highly conserved gene that provides a useful broad outline of species through to phylum level (Wilson et al. 1990, Stackebrandt & Goebel 1994). Species-level similarity is now recognised at 98.7% similarity or greater, i.e. divergence less than this threshold represents intra-species differences (Gevers et al. 2005, Stackebrandt & Ebers 2006, Yarza et al. 2014, Rosselló-Móra & Amann 2015). This was the basis of the first 16S haplotype designation in a *Liberibacter* species (Nelson et al. 2011). The very highly conserved nature of this gene means that more variable regions of the genome are used to describe within-haplotype differences (Matos et al. 2013, Yan et al. 2016, de Paula et al. 2019, Roberts et al. 2021, Cui et al. 2022) including prophage sequences (Zheng et al. 2016, Das et al. 2021) and the 16S-23S intergenic spacer region (Mukherjee et al. 2018).

Table 1: Currently known *Liberibacter* species with 16S rRNA gene sequences. Sequences from genome studies are marked * and those marked ** were partial sequences and excluded from the phylogenetic analysis.

Species	Short form	Sequence reference	Reference
“Ca. L. africanus”	Laf	CP004021 *	(Lin et al. 2015)
“Ca. L. americanus”	Lam	CP006604 *	(Wulff et al. 2014)
“Ca. L. asiaticus”	Las	CP001677 *	(Duan et al. 2009)
“Ca. L.” from Bhutan	Lbh	JACETX010000057 *	(Chambers et al. 2020)
“Ca. L. brunswickensis”	Lbr	KY077741	(Morris et al. 2017)
“Ca. L. caribbeanus”	Lcar	KP012551 **	(Keremane et al. 2015)
“Ca. L. capsica”	Lcap	OL221600 **	(Kwak et al. 2021)
<i>L. crescens</i>	Lcr	CP003789 *	(Leonard et al. 2012)
“Ca. L. ctenarytaina”	Lct	KX768754	(Thompson et al. 2017)
“Ca. L. europaeus”	Leu	PSQJ01000010 *	(Frampton et al. 2018)
“Ca. L. solanacearum” syn. <i>psyllauros</i>	Lso	KX431890.1 *	(Wang et al. 2017)

The *Liberibacter* species (Table 1) have three homogenous copies of the 16S gene (Nelson et al. 2015b) and haplotypes of this gene have been reported in some species (Nelson et al. 2011, 2015a, Nelson 2015, Haapalainen et al. 2020, Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020) although not in Las, the most widespread species (Nelson 2012, Moreno-Enríquez et al. 2014). These 16S haplotypes are highly unlikely to be expressing biological differences, but rather represent a commonality of other genetic elements. The haplotype definition in itself is a useful marker and should not be considered to define biological effects on the host species, nor even necessarily host-specific genetic adaptations (Nelson et al. 2013). However, haplotypes are associated with different plant or insect effects (Swisher Grimm et al. 2018, 2020, Harrison et al. 2018, Workneh et al. 2020) and even measured temporal prevalence (Workneh et al. 2018).

“*Candidatus Liberibacter europaeus*” (Leu) was initially identified from pear psyllids (*Cacopsylla pyrus* Linné, 1758). The pear tree hosts of the psyllids were symptomless, thus Leu was designated an

endophyte (Raddadi et al. 2011). Further investigation proved it to be widespread in Italy, Hungary and Israel, from *Cacopsylla* species and also from the breeding and overwintering plant hosts of these psyllids (Camerota et al. 2012). Unfortunately there were no sequences deposited from this study, but symptomless presence in plant hosts was confirmed. Shortly thereafter Leu was also discovered in New Zealand, but from symptomatic Scotch broom, *Cytisus scoparius* L. Link (Thompson et al. 2013). It was regarded as an accidental introduction to New Zealand from Britain in the introduced psyllid, *Arytainilla spartiophila* (Foerster, 1848), brought in to control broom (Weber et al. 2021, Fowler et al. 2021).

A preliminary analysis of ribosomal DNA sequences of Leu, available in GenBank, suggested the presence of two haplotypes based on single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the 16S and intergenic spacer region genes. In addition to the DNA evidence, there are apparent distinct geographic as well as psyllid and plant host species combinations. These were called LeuA (Italy in pear and associated psyllid) and LeuB (New Zealand from Scotch broom and associated psyllid, both imported from Britain) (Nelson 2015). This is similar to findings in Lso and Laf with their varying combinations of insect/plant hosts, and in the case of Lso, very widespread continental geographic range and geographic zones per haplotype (Nelson et al. 2011, 2015a, Haapalainen et al. 2020, Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020).

Since then, we have a broader range of sequences now available from Scotch broom and associated psyllids. This includes sequences from Britain (Tannières et al. 2020) as well as a Leu draft genome (Frampton et al. 2018). A sequence 100% identical to the Italian sequence (LeuA) and 99.3% similar to the broom-associated sequences (LeuB), was discovered in *Diaphorina* cf. *continua* (Loginova 1972) from Corsica. Like the pear plants, no symptoms were noted on the presumed psyllid host plant *Thymelaea tartonraira* (Thymelaeaceae) (Nakabachi et al. 2020). Of particular note is that this insect is a close relative of the Asian citrus psyllid, *D. citri* (Kuwayama 1908), a vector of Las and causing the devastating citrus disease Huanglongbing (HLB) (Bové 2014). A broad scan for secondary symbionts of psyllids in Japan resulted in identification of Leu in yet another psyllid, *Anomoneura mori* (Schwarz 1896). This sequence has 99.8% similarity with LeuA from Italy (Nakabachi et al. 2022). *A. mori* is the psyllid commonly associated with damage on mulberry plants (Ki & Par 2016).

Leu was recognised to be most closely related to “*Ca. L. americanus*” (Lam) (Raddadi et al. 2011) and thus an attempt was made to determine whether one putative haplotype was more closely related to Lam than the other (Nelson 2015). Unfortunately, available 16S sequences of Leu were not long enough to cover all of the more variable sites of this highly conserved gene, thus opening the door to some doubt on the veracity of this exercise. However, subsequent phylogenetic trees have shown the same closeness of Lam and Leu relative to the other *Liberibacter* species (Nakabachi et al. 2020, 2022, Thapa et al. 2020, Chambers et al. 2020).

We now have a number of Leu sequences available from four different laboratory investigations (Table 2). Further, we have a Leu full length 16S sequence, as well as from many of the other species (Table 1). The objective was therefore to update Leu 16S haplotype identification, and to update the position of Leu in the *Liberibacter* phylogeny using full 16S gene sequences extracted from genomes and including other more recently discovered species.

Table 2: *Leu* sequences and sources used for haplotype description.

Sequence id	Source	Region	Gene	Isolate	Reference
FN678792	<i>Cacopsylla pyri</i>	Italy	16S	NR-01	(Raddadi et al. 2011)
JX629241	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S	Chch2	(Thompson et al. 2013)
JX629242	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S	Chch3	
JX629243	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S	Chch4	
JX629244	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S	RakO	
JX244258	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S-23S	Psy6	
JX244259	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S-23S	BrS	
JX244260	<i>C. scoparius</i>	New Zealand	16S-23S	94B	
MN176610	<i>A. spartiophylla</i>	Britain	16S	PsyUK4	(Tannières et al. 2020)
PSQJ01000000	<i>A. spartiophylla</i>	New Zealand	Draft genome	ASNZ1	(Frampton et al. 2018)
QEYS00000000	<i>A. spartiophylla</i>	Britain	Draft genome	ASUK1	Unpublished Frampton et al 2018
TAAA01000007	<i>Diaphorina</i> cf. <i>continua</i>	Corsica	16S	dia_sv6	(Nakabachi et al. 2020)
TAAB01000035	<i>Anomoneura mori</i>	Japan	16S	SV33	(Nakabachi et al. 2022)

Methods

Sequences on GenBank/DDBJ were downloaded (Table 1, Table 2, Appendix). These were aligned in ClustalX using the default settings (Larkin et al. 2007) and segments of the downloaded sequence beyond the 5' or 3' ends were truncated to within the ~1500 bp 16S full gene length. Where known, all *Liberibacter* species use the common ATG start codon (Suzek et al. 2001) and the TAA stop codon prevalent in genomes with lower GC abundance (Rocha & Danchin 2002, Hartung et al. 2011, Korkmaz et al. 2014). Manual inspection in ClustalX was used to record SNP differences of the aligned *Leu* sequences. The intergenic spacer region included previously was excluded here, as there remains minimal new information, and this region is inherently more variable and therefore more suited to a finer resolution of investigation than appropriate for this species at present.

Alignment with tree visualisation was performed through the online pipeline <http://www.phylogeny.fr/> using the default “One Click” option (Dereeper et al. 2008). For the broader species phylogeny, species where only short lengths of the 16S gene are available were excluded.

Results

The extra sequences, available since the preliminary haplotype analysis, confirms the presence of the original two 16S haplotypes (Figure 1), and extends the analysis from two SNPs to four (Table 3). In addition, the mulberry psyllid sequence suggests a third haplotype at a fifth SNP position (proposed as LeuC), but arising from within LeuA. Comparison with the same positions on Lam suggests that LeuB might be the closest to the Leu haplotype common ancestor, and LeuC the furthest away (Table 3).

Table 3: Leu 16S haplotypes indicated by SNPs and nucleotides on the same position from Lam. na=not available.

Nucleotide number	Pear (Italy/Corsica) LeuA	Broom (Britain/NZ) LeuB	Mulberry (Japan) LeuC	Lam
70	A/na	G	na	G
565	C	T	C	T
571	C	C	T	C
586	G	A	G	T
661	G	A	G	A

The SNPs defining the three 16S haplotypes indicate near commonality but with full gene sequences available there are now four SNPs between the original LeuA and LeuB (Table 3). LeuC appears to have only a single SNP difference to LeuA, but unfortunately the available sequence does not cover position 70. Adding the equivalent positions from Lam, previously reported as the most closely related *Liberibacter* species, LeuB is likely closest to the common ancestor of the Leu and Lam species.

The expanded phylogenetic tree (Error: Reference source not found) confirms the previously reported closeness of Leu with Lam, forming a cluster with Lct. Lcr again is significant as the outlier species and not ancestral to the others, but is closest to the progenitor of all *Liberibacter* species and other species within the Rhizobiaceae. Interestingly, the TD pilus genes of Rhizobiaceae exhibit a similar phylogeny (Hansen et al. 2022 Fig. 4).

Figure 2: Phylogenetic tree of *Liberibacter* species with full 16S sequences available, plus *Martellella* and *Rhizobium* species as out group genera but also from within Rhizobiaceae. See Table 1 for full species names.

Discussion

Haplotype identification has led to some interesting insights into *Liberibacter* presence and movement. For example, North American Lso haplotypes are clearly geographically defined, although both occur in mainly solanaceous crops and related weed species (Nelson et al. 2011). In Europe and North Africa, Lso is generally only found in carrot family plants, but with a wide geographically defined distribution of many discrete Lso haplotypes (Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020). The associated psyllid species vary by common association between the psyllid and its plant host.

Laf haplotypes (or subspecies) are somewhat analogous in Africa, and generally associated with plants in the Rutaceae family (including non-native citrus crops) and their associated (native) psyllid species (Garnier et al. 2000, Nelson et al. 2015a, Roberts et al. 2015, Roberts & Pietersen 2017).

The standout here is Las where, despite an extremely wide geographic range of citrus crop infections and dire consequences for these crops (Bové & Nelson 2013, Bové 2014), no 16S haplotypes have been noted (Nelson 2012). Thus more variable regions of the genome, such as simple sequence repeats and prophages, have been used.

The Leu haplotypes are associated with specific geographic regions and specific plant/psyllid host species. This is very similar to the position noted for Lso and Laf. The currently somewhat limited sequence availability is very likely simply a reflection of limited surveillance of the species, especially in the absence of crop symptoms (Raddadi et al. 2011), while more work has been conducted in symptomatic weedy plants (Tannières et al. 2020). The presence of LeuA from Corsica in a *Diaphorina* species indicates this haplotype may be considerably more widespread geographically and across plant/insect host associations.

Confirmation of the two originally described haplotypes, LeuA and LeuB, is useful. Although the symptomatic LeuB in Scotch broom is not as damaging as Laf, Las and Lso in their crop hosts, it appears to add to the anticipated weed control associated with the broom psyllid (Hogg et al. 2016). How much is dependent on LeuB for these symptoms, as opposed to simply large psyllid populations, on these weeds is not known (Syrett et al. 2007, Fowler et al. 2021). LeuC, potentially a derivative of LeuA (Figure 1) is more likely on a separate evolutionary path, especially being discovered geographically distant and potentially quite a different psyllid/plant combination than LeuA. This is quite a different circumstance to the designation Cras1a and Cras1b as haplotype variants (Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020).

The discovery of Leu potentially associated with the important sericultural industry might spur further investigations, especially as mulberry yellow dwarf disease is of serious concern (Gai et al. 2015). While this is currently regarded as a phytoplasma infection, the potential for confusion where *Phytoplasma* and *Liberibacter* infection with similar symptoms in North American potato crops (Secor & Rivera-Varas 2004, Covarrubias et al. 2006), and dual infections with similar symptoms in carrot crops (Gera et al. 2011, Munyaneza et al. 2011, Satta et al. 2016) and citrus (Chen et al. 2009, Saberi et al. 2017, Ghosh et al. 2019, Luis-Pantoja et al. 2021), suggests a deeper search is warranted. However, the earlier suggestion that Leu might be related to Parry's disease or pear decline appears to be rather more settled as being a *Phytoplasma* infection (Davies et al. 1992, 1998, Seemüller & Schneider 2004).

Leu distribution records suggest a very broad Eurasian distribution, from Britain in the west (Tannières et al. 2020), through the Mediterranean regions, including Corsica, across to Israel (Raddadi et al. 2011, Camerota et al. 2012, Nakabachi et al. 2020), and east to Japan (Nakabachi et al. 2022). Thus essentially the full latitudinal breadth of Laurasia during the Jurassic era, with the closeness of Lam to Leu also supporting their ancestor having a Laurasian distribution (Nelson et al. 2013). An apparent oddity is Lct clustering with them, although currently only recorded from *Fuschia* species in New Zealand (Thompson et al. 2017).

Conclusion

The previous tentative description of 16S haplotypes of Leu, tentative because of the limited availability of sequences, is now readily confirmed. The symptomatic presence in Scotch broom plants indicates Leu may express symptoms in some plants, while other reports indicate it may be asymptomatic. Finally, Leu is confirmed within *Liberibacter* phylogeny as closest to Lam, but now also including Lct in the species cluster.

“First you guess,” Richard Feynman, 1964

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Appendix

FASTA format of 16S sequences

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